

Liver Disease Data Preprocessing Using Improved Relief Algorithm

Dr.R.Rangaraj¹, Nibin Mathew²

¹Associate Professor & Head, Department of Computer Science, Hindusthan College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore - 641028.

²Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, Hindusthan College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore - 641028.

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Abstract

Liver disease is a noticeable illness other than coronary failure, which is taking a great deal of lives. Since more often than not liver sickness is recognized at a later stage leading to death. The quantity of liver patients is expanding a direct result of a few reasons like overconsumption of liquor, breathing in damaging gas, consuming dirtied water, etc which can influence wellbeing parameters. Utilizing machine learning forecast models, liver diseases can be anticipated involving those wellbeing parameters in the beginning phases. To obtain improved results the investigation was finished utilizing an alternate data mining algorithm contrasted and past liver sickness predictions. This research work proposed enhanced pre-processing algorithm Improved Relief had been evaluated using performance evaluator measures. The proposed pre-processing algorithm has high impact on performance of ML algorithms.

Keywords: - Data analytics, predictive analytics, machine learning algorithms, preprocessing, Improved Relief algorithm, Prediction model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The liver is a significant organ of the human body and it is situated underneath the rib confine in the right upper midsection. It eliminates poisons from the body and maintains healthy blood sugar levels in the body. However body organs have self-recuperating limit, overconsumption of liquor and openness to sullied air and water influences the liver which prompts a higher pace of Liver disappointment. Liver transplantation is the arrangement however with greater expenses and a slower pace of progress. Recognizing the liver harm at the earliest can diminish the opportunity of liver disappointment.

Liver disease is likewise alluded to as a hepatic disease. Hepatic diseases produce side effects like sickness, regurgitating, weakness, stomach torment and enlarging, back agony, exhaustion and weight reduction. Certain patients are accounted for to experience the ill effects of jaundice (yellowing of the skin and eyes), liquid in strange cavity, pale stool, and particularly enlarged spleen as well as the gallbladder. Tests, for example, imaging tests and liver capacity tests can check for liver harm and assist with diagnosing liver diseases whether it is intense or constant [1]. The meaning of intense liver disease depends on length, with the historical backdrop of the disease, doesn't surpass a half year. Beginning phase HCC location and diagnosis can permit the patients to receive the treatment prior and accomplish better endurance rates. All the mainland and national liver disease social orders have suggested that reconnaissance ought to be done for high-risk patients with cirrhosis. Ultrasonography is the favored test for observation however is unsatisfactory due to the restrictions of ultrasound

administrator reliance and its low aversion to little liver tumors. Dynamic differentiation upgraded imaging is suggested as the first-line analytic instrument for HCC while the screening test result is unusual. Without a doubt, contrasted and computed tomography (CT), improved MRI is the better decision in view of its different tissue contrast systems and it is the best way to evaluate all major and auxiliary imaging highlights. Nonetheless, improved MRI couldn't be involved broadly like ultrasonography in screening and reconnaissance attributable to its significant expense and the gamble of differentiation related aftereffects.

As of late, artificial knowledge techniques have been utilized broadly in the clinical fields to work on the effectiveness of disease diagnosis/classification in its beginning phases [7]. Among those techniques stand apart machine learning techniques, which are a bunch of measurable models that assist the machine with gaining from past data [8]. Despite this, it is frequently hard to manage patient data for diagnosis in the beginning phases because of reasons like data volume, missing qualities and clamor in the data. Yet, machine learning techniques and their capabilities have helped process such data [9].

Data mining

Data mining is one of the locales of popular aptitude since it supports hide and every now and again graceful design in huge volumes of information. The true world big datasets are getting from various origins and include information that tends to be inconsistent, incomplete, and noisy.

Data were immediately taken from the origin will have errors, inconsistencies, or most significant, it is not willing to be considered for a data mining method. The disturbing numeral data in the business, late science, calls, and business applications to the prerequisite of extra muddled errands are dissected. In Data preprocessing, it is achievable to change the antagonistic into doable. Data preprocessing contain detecting, and data decrease strategies, diminishing the intricacy of the information, or uproarious elements from the information.

Accomplishing effective outcomes from the perform model in deep learning and machine learning design arrangement information to be in an appropriate scheme. Few specified deep learning and machine learning models require data in a identify format. An additional phase of analysis and data preparation is that the information set should be arranged in such a way that more than one deep learning and machine learning algorithms are executed in one information group, and the optimum out of them is preferred.

Figure 1. Steps in Data Preprocessing

- 1. Data profiling.** Data profiling is the process of examining, investigating and checking on data to gather insights about its quality. It starts with a survey of existing data and its characteristics. Data researchers recognize data sets that are relevant to the front and center issue, inventory its huge attributes, and structure a hypothesis of features that may be relevant for the proposed analytics or machine learning task. They likewise relate data sources to the significant business ideas and consider which preprocessing libraries could be utilized.
- 2. Data cleansing.** The point here is to track down the least demanding method for redressing quality issues, for example, killing terrible data, filling in missing data or in any case ensuring the crude data is reasonable for feature engineering.
- 3. Data reduction.** Raw data sets frequently incorporate redundant data that emerge from characterizing peculiarities in various ways or data that isn't pertinent to a specific ML, AI or analytics task. Data reduction uses techniques like principal component analysis to transform the raw data into a simpler form suitable for particular use cases.
- 4. Data transformation.** Here, data scientists think about how different aspects of the data need to be organized to make the most sense for the goal. This could include things like structuring unstructured data, combining salient variables when it makes sense or identifying important ranges to focus on.
- 5. Data enrichment.** In this step, data scientists apply the various feature engineering libraries to the data to effect the desired transformations. The result should be a data set organized to achieve the optimal balance between the training time for a new model and the required compute.
- 6. Data validation.** At this stage, the data is split into two sets. The first set is used to train a machine learning or deep learning model. The subsequent set is the trying data that is utilized to measure the exactness and robustness of the resulting model. This second step helps identify any problems in the hypothesis used in the cleaning and feature engineering of the data. On the off chance that the data researchers are happy with the outcomes, they can push the preprocessing undertaking to a data engineer who figures out how to scale it for production. If not, the data scientists can go back and make changes to the way they implemented the data cleansing and feature engineering steps.

2. EXISTING METHODOLOGY

1. Byeongwan Noh, Young Mok Park, Yujin Kwon, Chang in Choi, Byung Kwan Choi (2022) [7] et.al Machine learning-based survival rate prediction of Korean hepatocellular carcinoma patients using multi-center data. An amount of 10,742 patients with HCC was divided into two get-togethers, with Group I (2920 patients) certified on biopsy and Group II (5562 patients) examined as HCC as per HCC definite principles as outlined in Korean Liver Cancer Association rules. The data were displayed by features of patient clinical qualities. Features successful in foreseeing perseverance rate were analyzed brilliantly. Different machine learning strategies were utilized. By fostering a prescient model utilizing machine learning algorithms to foresee the visualization of HCC patients, it is feasible to extend enhanced treatment by case according to liver capacity and growth status. To settle the impediments of multi-focus data gathered in a standardized structure is the need of national multi-focus data management.

2. Satish Chandra Reddy Nandipati, HaziqahShamsudin, Chew XinYing (2019)[16] et.al proposed **Synthetic minority over-sampling technique**, Classification and Feature Selection Approaches by Machine Learning Techniques: Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) Prognosis Prediction. Hepatocellular carcinoma would one say one is of the most well-known liver

disease passings around the world, which is overwhelming in Asian and African nations? It is assessed that the endurance rate can be expanded with the early location; subsequently it is essential to anticipate the chose highlights to keep away from this disease. The classification model prediction, and to recognize the job of elements chose utilizing Rapid digger machine learning administrators is the point of this review. The exactness of the SVM algorithm is viewed as highest at 81.81%, trailed by irregular backwoods (79.67%) in the classification model, while in highlight choice both Naïve Bayes and SVM show comparable correctnesses (74.90 and 74.10 %). During the preprocessing stage the missing qualities were ascribed by utilizing HEOM distance and K-implies bunching was applied, later synthetic minority over-sampling strategy (SMOTE) technique was applied to get the balanced dataset. Both neural networks and strategic relapse algorithms were applied to the balanced dataset. During preprocessing a Markov Blanket based bunching strategy was applied, where the overt repetitiveness among the highlights is computed in light of the positioning. A total of six distinct classifiers were utilized to concentrate on the evaluation of the proposed technique.

3. V. Bhagat, B. Robins and P. M.O (2019)[1] et.al proposed Sparx - Data Preprocessing Module. The data stream between the edge and the cloud can be improved as far as effectiveness, unwavering quality and heredity by preprocessing the datasets nearer to their data sources. They propose a devoted data preprocessing structure that conveys preprocessing undertakings between a cloud stage and two edge stages to make a data stream with logically working on quality. The system handles heterogeneous data and dynamic preprocessing plans simultaneously zeroing in on arranged applications and use cases from different regions. Their methodology limits the responsibility on focal foundations and lessens the assets utilized for moving raw data from the edge. We likewise demonstrate that preprocessing data can be sensor-explicit instead of utilization explicit and hence can be performed preceding knowing a particular application. We plan to broaden the variety of the data gathered to incorporate sound signs and video transfers straightforwardly from associated cameras and mouthpieces. We are additionally hoping to address data security and reasonableness and send preprocessing assignments that wipe out databases and protect personal data at the edge.

4. S. B. Kotsiantis, D. Kanellopoulos and P. E. Pintelas (2014)[5] et.al proposed Data Preprocessing for Supervised Learning. Many factors influence the progress of Machine Learning (ML) on a given undertaking. The portrayal and nature of the occasion data are as a matter of some importance. Assuming that there is a lot of unimportant and excess data present or boisterous and untrustworthy data, then, at that point, information disclosure during the training stage is more troublesome. It is notable that data planning and sifting steps take a considerable amount of processing time in ML issues. Data pre-processing incorporates data cleaning, standardization, change, include extraction and selection, and so forth. The product of data pre-processing is the final training set. It would be great if a solitary succession of data pre-processing algorithms had the best performance for every data set yet this doesn't occur. In this manner, we present the most surely understand algorithms for each progression of data pre-processing with the goal that one accomplishes the best performance for their data set. As a rule, missing data ought to be pre-processed to permit the entire data set to be processed by a managed ML algorithm. Besides, a large portion of the current ML algorithms can extricate information from data sets that store discrete highlights. Assuming the highlights are ceaseless, the algorithms can be incorporated with a discretization algorithm that transforms them into discrete characteristics.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Data Preprocessing

Data Preprocessing is a fundamental stage during data mining. It is any kind of processing performed on raw data to change it into formats that are more straightforward to use for examination. In reality, data is habitually messy - missing key qualities, containing irregularities or showing "noise" (containing errors and outliers). Without data preprocessing, these data mistakes will get by and bring down the quality of data mining.

Preprocessing techniques include following tasks

- Data reduction: The dataset produced after this stage is more modest than the raw dataset, which further develops data mining effectiveness. It incorporates the selection of pertinent data by eliminating oddities and dispensing with duplicate values.
- Quality data generation: It changes over raw data into quality data, which helps for investigation. The quality of data can be worked on by recuperating deficient data. Filling missed values to decrease uncertainty does this. It tends to be made unadulterated by settling errors and eliminating outliers. Data clashes can be taken out by utilizing space information or master choice to settle disparities.
- Resolve redundancy.
- Correct inconsistencies.

Directed Acyclic Graph

The point of Boolean element examination (BFA) is to decay a $n \times m$ binary matrix I into a Boolean product $A \circ B$ of a $n \times k$ binary matrix A and a $k \times m$ binary matrix B with k as little as could really be expected. Consequently, rather than m unique ascribes, one expects to track down k new properties, called factors. Review that a binary (or Boolean) matrix is a matrix whose sections are 0 or 1. A Boolean matrix product $A \circ B$ of binary matrices A and B is characterized by

$$A(\circ B)_{ij} = \bigvee_{l=1}^k A_{il} \cdot B_{lj},$$

Where $\bigvee$ denotes maximum and $\cdot$ is the usual product. The interpretation of matrices A and B is: $A_{il} = 1$ means that factor l applies to object i and $B_{lj} = 1$ means that attribute j is one of the manifestations of factor l . Then $A \circ B$ says: "object i have attribute j if and only if there is a factor l such that l applies to i and j is one of the manifestations of l ".

The (solution to the) problem of decomposing binary matrices was recently described by means of formal concept analysis [1]. The description lies in an observation that matrices A and B can be constructed from a set F of formal concepts of I . In particular, if $\mathcal{B}(X, Y, I)$ is the concept lattice of I , with $X = \{1 \dots n\}$ and $Y = \{1, \dots, m\}$, and

$$\mathcal{F} = \{ \langle A_1, B_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle A_k, B_k \rangle \} \subseteq \mathcal{B}(X, Y, I),$$

then for the $n \times k$ and $k \times m$ matrices AF and BF defined in such a way that the l -th column $(AF)_l$ of AF consists of the characteristic vector of A_l and the l -th row $(BF)_l$ of BF consists of the characteristic vector of B_l , the following universality theorem holds:

Theorem 1: For every I there is $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{B}(X, Y, I)$ such that $I = AF \circ BF$. Besides, decompositions involving formal ideas as factors are ideal in that they yield the most un-number of factors conceivable:

Theorem 2: Let $I = A \circ B$ for $n \times k$ and $k \times m$ binary matrices A and B . Then there exists a set $F \subseteq B(X, Y, I)$ of formal concepts of I with $|F| < k$ such that for the $n \times |F|$ and $|F| \times m$ binary matrices AF and BF we have $I = AF \circ BF$.

Formal concepts F are called factor concepts. Each factor concept determines a factor. For the constructive proof of the last theorem, examples and further results, we refer to [1].

Reducing the collection of attributes

The second of this two methods consists in the replacement of original attributes by factors. Hence the new collection of attributes Y' is defined to be $Y' = F$ and the new data table $I' \subseteq X * Y'$ is put to $I' = A$. The new reduced data table for example data in Fig. 1 is thus a table depicted. Restricted to attributes $f_1, \dots, f_6$.

Since the number of factors is usually smaller than the number of attributes, see [1], the transformation of objects from attribute space to the factor space usually leads to the reduction of dimensionality of data. However, the transformation is not an injective mapping, see [1] for details. Namely, for two distinct objects $x_1, x_2 \in X$ described by different vectors in the space of attributes and different class labels assigned, the representation of both x_1, x_2 by vectors in the factor space might be the same.

Consider the relation $\ker(g)$ (the kernel relation of g) describing such a situation. We select the class label assigned to each object $x \in X$ in the new data table I' to be the majority class label for the class $[x]_{\ker(g)} \in X/\ker(G)$

Finally, the decision tree is induced from the transformed data table $I' \in XXF$. Similarly as in the first method from section III-B, when classifying an object x , we first compute the description of the object by factors F as a vector $g(P_2) \in \{0,1\}^k$ in the factor space and the object described by $g(P_x)$ is classified by the decision tree. In this example, the decision tree induced from reduced data table (the table in Fig. 3 restricted to attributes $f_1, \dots, f_6$) is the same as the tree induced from the extended data table, i.e. the tree depicted (right).

Missing value imputation

A common practice in this research is the use of mean, and median for imputing missing values. However, these methods are highly likely to increase data bias [36]. Another method is that of multiple imputations of missing values (MICE). This method is known to surpass the mean and median approaches; however, MICE suffer from performance degradation in the presence of nonlinearities in predictor variables. In this paper, we employ a predictive approach to missing value imputation using PR which is a nonlinear regressor. The input to the missing value imputation process is the subset of the PIMA Indian dataset with only selected features. The steps are as follows:

The percentage of missing qualities for each chose include, right off the bat, is looked at over a decision threshold of 5%. The decision is: in the event that the quantity of no passages in the subset data is more prominent than 5%, PR is applied; in any case, the section is eliminated. From the PIMA cancer dataset, Insulin is seen to have above 5% zero sections.

Furthermore, the component from the subset data that exceptionally corresponds to Insulin turns into the predictor variable for anticipating Insulin. The variable is Glucose.

In conclusion, the data points are partitioned into nonzero and zero sets, where the nonzero set is utilized for preparing and testing while the zero set is anticipated. The resulting output is joined with the nonzero set to shape the last dataset.

The data pre-processing phase handles missing, null value and outlier data. Then dimensionality reduction has been applied to data. Normalizing the information values for each characteristic estimated in the training occurrences will help to upgrade the effectiveness

of the learning phase. Particularly for the distance-based techniques normalization upholds attributes with huge ranges from out weighting attributes with at first more modest ranges. The normalization score is considered and it is called as z-score. Further improved relief algorithm is combined.

Improved Relief Algorithm With DAG

Input: training instance set S, a vector of features, class value

m – – – Number of training instances

f – – – Number of features

Parameter:

n – – Number of random training instances out of *m* update weight

Algo:

Initialize all features weights $W|A| = 0.0$

For each *k* = 1 *to* *n* *do*

Randomly select a target instance *R_k*

Find the nearest hit *M_H* *and nearest miss* (*instance*)

For *A* = 1 *to* *f* *do*

$W|A| = W|A| - diff(A, R_k, M_H) / n^+$

End for

End For

In order to classify the classes and predict the target value machine learning supervised algorithms are used. Some most frequently used popular algorithms concept of learning principles and formula calculations are discussed briefly in the following sections

4. EXPERIMENT RESULT

The trial settings for assessing the proposed machine learning framework for cancer expectation are the assessment of the proposed data preprocessing techniques inside the ML system, execution assessment of different machine learning classifiers with and without optimization and seriousness assessment of the best model in cancer prediction, performance evaluation of the proposed deep learning model performance across datasets, and comparison with the state-of-the-art. Performance in each setting is evaluated using the following metrics: sensitivity, precision, F1-score, specificity, and accuracy which are briefly discussed in the following subsections.

Specificity

This is the proportion of patients with no cancer, the negative instances, who are distinguished just like no liver disease and it is computed as the proportion of true negatives (TN) to the sum of TN and false positives (FP).

$$Speciicity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

Dataset	SMOTE	DAG	Proposed Algorithm	Improved	Relief
50	89.04	86.37	98.45		
100	85.89	82.82	96.36		
150	81.52	81.74	94.91		

200	76.65	78.65	91.38
250	77.91	74.42	89.92

Table 1. Comparison table for Specificity

The Comparison table 1 of Specificity Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 76 to 89, 74 to 87 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 89 to 99. The proposed method provides the great results.

Figure2. Comparison table for Specificity

The Comparison Figure 2 of Specificity Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm, provides the better results. X axis denote the Dataset and y axis denotes the Specificity ratio. The existing algorithm values start from 76 to 89, 74 to 87 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 89 to 99. The proposed method provides the great results.

Sensitivity

This is the proportion of patients with liver disease, the positive instances, who are accurately recognized as being liver disease and it is computed as the proportion of true positives (TP) to the amount of TP and false negatives (FN).

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Dataset	SMOTE	DAG	Proposed Improved Relief Algorithm
50	75	85	99
100	72	78	97
150	68	72	94
200	71	69	92
250	65	63	91

Table 2. Comparison table for Sensitivity

The Comparison table 2 of Sensitivity Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 65 to 75, 63 to 85 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 91 to 99. The proposed method provides the great results.

Figure 3. Comparison table for Sensitivity

The Comparison Figure 3 of Sensitivity Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm, provides the better results. X axis denote the Dataset and y axis denotes the Sensitivity ratio. The existing algorithm values start from 65 to 75, 63 to 85 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 91 to 99. The proposed method provides the great results.

Precision

This is the proportion of patients with liver disease, the positive instances, who are correctly identified as being liver disease out of all the liver disease patients and is computed as the ratio of TP to the sum of TP and false positives (FP).

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Dataset	SMOTE	DAG	Proposed Improved Relief Algorithm
50	76.63	66.94	88.01
100	78.91	69.66	91.87
150	83.26	74.12	93.48
200	81.45	79.09	94.23
250	84.33	86.38	96.52

Table 3. Comparison table for Precision

The Comparison table 3 of Precision Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm, provides the better results. The existing algorithm values start from 66.94 to 86.38 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 88.01 to 96.52. The proposed method provides the great results.

Figure 4. Comparison Chart for Precision

The Comparison figure 4 of Precision Values explains the different values of existing SMOTE, DAG and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm. While comparing the Existing algorithm and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm provides the better results. X axis denote the Dataset and y axis denotes the Precision ratio. The existing algorithm values start from 66.94 to 86.38 and proposed Improved Relief Algorithm values starts from 88.01 to 96.52. The proposed method provides the great results.

5. CONCLUSION

Selected public real-world datasets from UCI Machine Learning Repository [11] were used in the experiments. Basic characteristics of the datasets are depicted in Tab. I. The numbers of attributes are of original categorical attributes and, in brackets, of binary attributes after nominal scaling. The experiments were done using the 10- fold stratified cross-validation test. The following results are of averaging 10 execution runs of model learning on each dataset fold with randomly ordered records.

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